

EXPLANATORY NOTES FOR THE RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT SUPPORTED SELF-EVALUATION INSTRUMENT FOR HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTES AND RESEARCH PERFORMING ORGANISATIONS

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This document constitutes the explanatory notes for the Research Data Management Supported Self-Evaluation Instrument for Higher Education Institutes and Research Performing Organisations, referred to hereafter as the “instrument”; the self-evaluation spreadsheet template, referred to hereafter as the “spreadsheet template” and the template for producing the results report, referred to hereafter as the “results template”.

The instrument has been developed to allow higher education institutions and research performing organisations to evaluate their research data management capability maturity.

The instrument is designed to gather information that can be used with the spreadsheet template to produce charts and graphs which can then be inserted into the results template and produce a report on the maturity the subject organisation has reached for research data management support. The maturity report will detail how the organisation scores against a range of criteria – detailed below. These scores can be used in conjunction with an institution’s own strategic plans to identify areas where they can develop their practice further. It is recommended that a response is developed in light of the maturity report and this is fed into the institutions strategic development planning cycle.

These explanatory notes, the instrument, the spreadsheet template and the results template have been developed in the iFrame project funded through Ireland’s National Open Research Forum (NORF) under the 2023 Open Research Fund.

The purpose of this document is to provide guidance on the use of the instrument, the spreadsheet template and the results template and to provide a description of the method and methodological justifications for the design of the instrument.

Conducting the exercise

The instrument is designed to be completed by a suitable librarian and / or research support staff member within the subject organisation (referred to hereafter as the respondent) working in concert with an external researcher. The process to complete the instrument and produce a report is a collaborative activity and will entail a number of meetings between the researcher and the respondent.

It is recommended that the following process is followed:

1. The instrument, results template and these explanatory notes should be provided to the respondent in advance of any meeting, with enough time for the respondent to read through the instrument and gather information they may need to answer the questions. The respondent should be asked to draft a brief statement summarising the research data management support at their institution.
2. One or more support meetings (either face to face or virtual) should be arranged between the researcher and the respondent. At these meeting the researcher and

respondent should work through the questions, selecting the most fitting answer and adding contextual information. If any required information is not readily available, a further meeting may be held to confirm any issues or add additional information. The question can be addressed in any order that is agreeable to the researcher and respondent.

3. Once the researcher and respondent are in agreement, the completed instrument is signed-off.
4. The researcher will collate the information from the completed instrument and using the spreadsheet template and results template produce a short report that details the institution's scores and incorporates the contextual information. This report is shared with the respondent and the information provided can be expanded upon or contextualised as needed. This may take one or more meetings. When both the researcher and the respondent are satisfied, the report is signed off. It is a collaborative document that is jointly authored by the researcher and the respondent. The report can then be shared with the respondent's institution and wider as fitting.

The guiding principle is that the report is a collaborative and agreed upon document authored by the researcher and the respondent.

Structure of the instrument

The instrument consists of an initial free text area to provide a summary of the research data management support at the institution and then 18 question topics. Each question topic entails a main question with six possible answers, a supplementary question concerning the 'location' of the activity – whether it occurs at the research group level, at the departmental / school / faculty level, at the university level or tied to an external agency and a free-text section to add any contextual information that is felt to be pertinent to the question topic.

The possible answers to each main question are scored from one to six with one being the least mature and six being the most mature. For each question, the answer that most closely describes their organisation should be selected. If it is felt that more than one answer partly matches the organisation and / or no single answer matches completely, then the one answer that is the best fit should be selected.

Evaluating the information provided by the instrument and using the report template.

The report template provides a suggested framework for presenting the results from the completed instrument. It consists of eight sections that can be populated with charts and tables produced from the information provided in the signed-off instrument using the spreadsheet template and a written analysis of the results.

To produce the charts and tables it is suggested that the spreadsheet template is used.

To produce the charts, fill in tab one of the spreadsheet template with the scores for the 18 questions in the signed off instrument. This will auto-populate tabs 2-8 and the charts can then be copied to the relevant sections of the results template.

The results template has the following sections:

- Section 1 consists of a short statement by the respondent summarising the research data management support at their institution
- Section 2 is a summary of the numerical choice for each question and a graphical representation of the frequency of the scores. The table presents each score and Min, Max and Arithmetic Mean for each stage and each area. The frequency distribution has been calculated using the FREQUENCY function in Excell with six 'bins' ladled 1-6. The resultant table of data has been presented as a graph.
- Section 3 are graphical representations of the results for the three key areas (the Policies, Procedures and Documentation; the Technological Environment and Infrastructure and Human Capacity and Resources) arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle.
- Section 4 are graphical representations of the scores for the different stages in the research data life cycle by area.
- Section 5 is a graphical representation of the collated results of the three key areas arranged by the stages or phases in the research life cycle.
- Section 6 are graphical representations of i) the results organised comparatively for the stage of the research life-cycle arranged by the three key areas and ii), the areas arranged by the research life-cycle.
- Section 7 are tables showing the variance between the scores for the stages within each key area and between the areas within each stage.
- Section 8 are graphical representations of the location of the unit that determines practice in each area and in each stage.

The Analysis section draws upon the statistical data and contextual information to identify any useful patterns and areas that may warrant further investigation and action.

Research design

The research design for this project was developed to address research questions concerning the provision of support for research data management in Irish higher education and research performing organisations.

As noted above, the project has been funded by Ireland's National Open Research Forum (NORF) and as such we have sought to align the underpinning ethos of the project with the values espoused by NORF and in particular the FAIR research principles. Accordingly, the methodology, selection of data collection and analytical methods and approach to dissemination are informed by three principles:

1. **Openness** – that the 'machinery' of the research and the decisions involved in the research instrument design are evident and accessible.
2. **Collaboration** – that the research be a joint-venture between the subject institution and the researcher. This will be reflected in the design of the study, the process of data capture and analysis and in the attribution in the dissemination.
3. **Research process focus** – that the project is designed to address the aspects of research data management that are needed for the research data lifecycle and interaction with the organisation.

Following a review of literature and analysis of international best practice, it was evident that maturity models are a widely used and accepted means of assessing research data management capability. The maturity model approach originates in a process to evaluate vendors tendering for contracts to supply bespoke software to the US Department of Defense (Humphrey, 1988). Maturity referred to the extent to which a company had organised and optimised its processes to achieve a specific aim. In such models, maturity is understood as a scale with a lack of activity at one end and "the state of being complete, perfect or ready" (Mettler, Rohner and Winter, 2010) at the other. Since their initial use, maturity models have been extensively developed and deployed across a range of industries.

Due to their frequent use in scholarship on research data management, maturity models constitute a well-understood mechanism for evaluating research data management practices within institutes of higher education and research performing organisations. Their use is widely accepted as a means to interrogate an organisation's development with research data management and has been deployed in a number of published studies (Qin, Crowston and Kirkland, 2017; Cox *et al.*, 2019; Fry *et al.*, 2023; Harguem and Boubaker, 2023). Such direct applicability to the nature of the research, their currency with the research data management community and their ease of understanding makes maturity models an appropriate device to structure the capture and analysis of data. However, the development of maturity models incorporates specific judgements and decisions such as the definitions of the levels of maturity, the scale of measurement and the dimensions of the concepts measured (Lasrado, Vatrappu and Andersen, 2015). In some instances, such information is not

explicit in the models used. Such lack of openness is felt to challenge the principles of ethical transparency and in particular the aspect of analytic transparency - that researchers will make available how evidence is measured interpreted and analysed (Moravcsik, 2020).

In the acquisition of data from institutions to determine maturity levels, studies have adopted a variety of approaches such as post-positivist mixed methods (Mthembu and Ocholla, 2024), bibliometrics (Mulongo *et al.*, 2022), structured interviews (Van Gulick and Borghi, 2017), surveys (Cox *et al.*, 2017) and self-evaluation (Rans and Whyte, 2017). Such research methods typically involve an external researcher conducting research upon a subject institution availing of information through a variety of means. In some cases (Mulongo *et al.*, 2022) the means of enquiry were unobtrusive and the subject organisations were not made aware that they were being scrutinized. In other cases, a researcher engaged with representatives of the organisations being investigated. Methods such as structured interviews (Van Gulick and Borghi, 2017) and surveys (Cox *et al.*, 2017) were used to collect data from recipients that could be collated and analysed to produce results. In these instances, data was collected by a researcher from the subject organisation, was then analysed externally and then disseminated. In certain cases the organisations were anonymised (Cox *et al.*, 2017) but in others the data was published and results between universities and countries contrasted (Mulongo *et al.*, 2022).

Mindful of the principles of Openness, Collaboration and Research Process Focus for the project and addressing the concerns noted above, the research design involves the researcher and respondent working together to produce a research report on the subject organisations support for research data management. The data used in the report is obtained by the researcher and respondent collaboratively completing a research instrument developed to determine the maturity of the organisation's support for research data management.

The report provides numerical and graphical representations of the responses and collations of the responses. This information is used to provide a short analysis.

Maturity model

Central to the instrument is a model of maturity developed to consider the support offered by subject organisations at the various stages of the research data lifecycle. Lasrado et al (Lasrado, Vatrappu and Andersen, 2015) noted maturity models often comprise of a scale of different levels, a selection of categories that can be used to frame questions and dimensions that may cut across questions.

Scale

In the original model the scale ran from zero to five (Humphrey, 1988), while in a number of more recent iterations this scale has been reduced to 0-3. For the purposes of numerical analysis used in this study the scale has been revised to run from one to six.

Level one: Incomplete – No activity in question occurring.

Level two: Initial – Practice may be occurring but is happenstance and unplanned. It may be unpredictable and reactive.

Level three: Managed – Practice is intended, may be simple and lacking full exposition.

Level four: Defined – Practice is proactive, fully documented and homogeneous across the organisation.

Level five: Quantitatively Managed – data is collected and collated about performance of practice and monitored.

Level six: Optimising – the organisation is geared towards improving its practice and the maturity offers stability which allows agile responsiveness.

The different levels indicate the extent to which an organisation engages with a task, recognises the requirements, develops means by which the task can be repeated and managed and how information on the performance of the task can be utilised in enhancing the organisation.

Categories and questions

The categories used in the model operate along two axis; the three areas of key provision and the six stages in the research life cycle. This results in 18 questions.

		Axis One Key Areas of Provision		
		Policies, procedures and documentation	Technological environment and infrastructure	People and human capacity
Axis Two	Fund	Question 1.1	Question 2.1	Question 3.1
	Plan and Design	Question 1.2	Question 2.2	Question 3.2
	Collect and Create	Question 1.3	Question 2.3	Question 3.3
	Analyse	Question 1.4	Question 2.4	Question 3.4
	Disseminate	Question 1.5	Question 2.5	Question 3.5
	Evaluate	Question 1.6	Question 2.6	Question 3.6

Axis one – research life cycle stages

The first axis are stages in the research data lifecycle. For the purposes of this study, the research data life cycle is understood to have six phases: Fund, Plan and Design, Collect and Create, Analyse, Disseminate and Evaluate.

Fund

The *fund* stage of the research involves preparing funding applications and securing appropriate financial resources to conduct and complete the research. For the purposes of this study, it involves ensuring that research data management is adequately addressed in funding applications and decision making.

Plan and Design

The *plan and design* phase of research involves the preparatory stages of research. In terms of research data management, it will involve tasks such preparing a data management plan, planning how data will be stored, ensuring the appropriate technological systems are in place to facilitate data management and ensuring appropriate staff are in place to facilitate research data management and that training is in place for them.

Collect and Create

The *collect and create* phase of the research lifecycle involves gathering and generating data or materials to address research questions. This phase includes designing and running experiments, conducting surveys, interviews or observations and collecting and producing primary or secondary data. It may also involve creating new datasets, prototypes, models or works of art.

Analyse

The *analyse* phase of the research lifecycle focuses on interpreting and making sense of collected data to answer research questions or test hypotheses. This phase involves applying statistical, qualitative, or computational methods to identify patterns, trends, and relationships and interpretative techniques to develop understanding. Researchers use tools such as software, coding frameworks, or theoretical models to derive insights. Critical evaluation ensures data validity, reliability and generalisability and address limitations or bias.

Disseminate

The *disseminate* phase of the research lifecycle involves sharing research findings and research data with relevant audiences to maximize their impact. This phase includes publishing results in academic monographs and edited collections, academic journals, presenting at conferences, creating reports and / or using media platforms like broadcast media such as radio and television programs, websites, podcasts or social media and making research data produced in the conduct of research available through appropriate channels such as data repositories.

Evaluate

The *evaluate* phase of the research life cycle involves assessing the quality, impact, and effectiveness of the research process and outcomes. Researchers critically review methodologies, data integrity, and conclusions to ensure validity and reliability. This phase

includes peer-review, feedback from stakeholders, and analysing metrics such as citations, societal impact or policy influence.

Axis two – key areas

The second axis are the forms of provision for research data management support within higher education organisations. For the purposes of this study, these are grouped into three distinct areas: Policies, Procedures and Documentation; Technological Environment and Infrastructure and support for People and Human Capacity.

Policies, Procedures and Documentation

This area relates to the support for research data management from the organisations policies, procedures and documentation. This includes both specific and indirect policies that impact research data, procedures to carry out and conduct processes and supporting documentation such as exemplar documents.

Responses are organised along two themes; first, the presence and extent of policies, procedures and documentation. Second, the way the policies, procedures and documentation are used in research data management.

Technological Environment and Infrastructure

This area relates to the support for research data management present in the information technology and general infrastructural environment. It may include services such as computer software, IT equipment such as high performance computing, laboratory equipment for data capture and media resources to record data and other specialist technology.

Responses are organised along four themes; first, recognition of the requirements for research data management; second, the ability to determine requirements; third the provision, fourth the impact of the provision.

People and Human Capacity

This area relates to the support for research data management afforded by the human capacity and people in the organisation. It may include the skills people possess, the training available in the organisation and the way in which the organisation deploys its workforce.

Responses are organised along four themes; first, recognition of the skills needed for research data management ; second, employing people with the required skills; third providing training, fourth having workload systems in place to afford research data management.

Question format design.

The questions are presented through asking which of a range of answers best matches the respondent's organisations. This approach and the visual design used is derived from the

Prince2 Maturity Model ('PRINCE2 Maturity Model P2MM v2.1 - Self Assessment .pdf', no date).

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